

REQUIREMENTS AND TASK DEFINITION

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Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D1.1 – Requirements and task definition” of the Horizon Europe project “eCREAM enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction” (hereinafter also referred to as “eCREAM”, project number: 101057726).

The document aims to outline the necessary elements to set up the Natural Language Processing (NLP) component within the Work Package 1 of the project. More precisely, this deliverable reports on Task 1.1, “Context analysis and task definition”, aiming to analyze the requirements for applying NLP techniques to the unstructured portion of EHRs in EDs and the definition of the NLP tasks useful for emergency physicians and nurses. According to the project plan, the task includes the following activities:

- *Analysis of the context and the requirements for each emergency department of the project* (Section 2). There are three main aspects we have been working on: an initial workflow involving the NLP component, in collaboration with Astir (Section 2.1); an anonymization component ensuring that the NLP component manages data without sensible information during the training of the model (Section 2.2); an initial study of the hardware requirements of the NLP component at inference time, in order to test the compatibility with current hardware available in EDs (Section 2.3).
- *Assessment and selection of the reference resources to be used for NLP processing* (Section 3). We are considering two kinds of resources: non-annotated resources, necessary for pre-training large language models in the medical domain (Section 3.1) and annotated resources, necessary to train a language model on the specific tasks of eCREAM (Section 3.2).
- *Definition of the NLP task, in terms of the clinical entities to be automatically extracted* (Section 4). In the first year of the project here we have been working on the following aspects: in collaboration with IRFMN and Orobix, we have provided a definition of the eCREAM tasks related to NLP, presented as the eCREAM benchmark (Section 4.1); an assessment of the available language models in the medical domain, including initial work on a T5-large medical model (Section 4.2).

1. Introduction

Work Package 1 (Natural Language Processing for EHR) of eCREAM aims to develop state-of-the-art NLP technologies for the six languages of the project (English, Greek, Italian, Polish, Slovakian, and Slovenian), able to interpret Electronic Health Record (EHR) content and to extract crucial information (metadata) from them, which will then be used to make accurate analysis and prediction.

More specifically, the objectives of WP1 include the following tasks:

- collect and annotate domain data for training NLP models;
- develop state-of-the-art NLP models based on deep learning architectures;
- assess models’ performance and refine the models;
- integrate the NLP models into the eCREAM platform for real-time processing.

To allow an incremental release of results, WP1 is organized along two cycles of activity, each including data collection, NLP development, evaluation and deployment.

For task 1.1 of this WP an analysis of the requirements for applying NLP techniques to the unstructured portion of EHRs in Emergency Departments (EDs) has been performed and the definition of the NLP tasks useful for emergency physicians and nurses has been laid out.

To achieve this task, the following steps have been followed:

- analysis of the context and the requirements for the Emergency Departments of the project;
- assessment and selection of the reference resources to be used for coding;
- definition of the NLP tasks, in terms of the clinical entities to be automatically extracted.

The outcomes of the task will be the basis for the NLP activities performed in the following tasks.

The context analysis has been carried out by IRFMN and FBK, involving the clinical partners of eCREAM, in order to assess the situation in each country.

Pre-trained multilingual language models (LMs) have become the standard approach in performing various NLP tasks. Application of NLP tasks in specialized domains (such as medicine) can benefit from the use of specialized LMs. Unfortunately, specialized LMs exist for English but not for other languages (such as the ones dealt with in eCREAM, Greek, Italian, Polish, Slovakian, and Slovenian). This fact calls for the creation of a multilingual LM for the medical domain. This involves various steps: identification of a specific LM, collection of a large amount of unannotated textual data (the more the better), construction of the LM, continual learning, fine-tuning for specific tasks (exploiting annotated data), application to texts, etc.

Another crucial element in the application of NLP technologies to EHRs involves the need for anonymization of the clinical documents to be compliant with the privacy regulations of the EU, in particular, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To address this issue, the project will buy licenses of an anonymization software developed by MAIZE. Such licenses will be used to install the anonymization software in the Emergency Departments participating in the assessment of the NLP tools.

2. Analysis of the context and the requirements for EDs

● 2.1 NLP workflow

The eCREAM data processing is organized in four steps, as you can see in figure 1:

1. Gathering of data from the Emergency Department database - it is performed by the Communication Adapter, the API Manager, the Interoperability Application and the Staging database
2. Pre-elaboration of data in order to create an homogeneous and minimized (according to the privacy rules) database - it is carried out by the Semantic Transformation, the NLP and the Target Database modules
3. Elaboration according to the Use Case 1 and 2 - it is done by the modules of Data Analysis and KPI elaboration
4. Presentation of the results to the end users - it is allowed by the Citizens App and the Dashboards for the Policymakers

Figure 1. Overall workflow of eCREAM.

The NLP eCREAM module will have a central part in step 2: as better shown in Figure 2, it will have the responsibility of extracting specific information from the textual data that are crucial for the UC1 elaboration.

- Use Case 1 needs to run its elaborations on logistic information regarding the Emergency Department and on clinical information about patients with dyspnea or transient loss of consciousness: NLP will be used to gather the latter from text data and clinical documents provided by the EDs’ EHRs, and at the same time to filter out all the personal data contained in them, so that the eCREAM central database will archive only pseudonymised data.

NLP will not be used in the Use Case 2 data flow because it will process only logistic information on the ED patient flow.

● 2.2 Anonymization component

A crucial element in the application of NLP technologies to EHRs involves the need for anonymization of the clinical documents to be compliant with the privacy regulations of the EU, in particular, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To address this issue, the project will buy licenses for an anonymization software developed by MAIZE. Such licenses will be used to install the anonymization software in the Emergency Departments participating in the assessment of the NLP tools.

The anonymization will take place before the textual portions of EHRs are analyzed by the NLP tools and will involve the following entities: person names, locations, and phone numbers. To assess the effectiveness of the anonymization module, a set of fictitious EHRs has been developed and EHRs annotated. Such annotated documents are split into 2 parts: the former will be used during the development of the tool, and the latter will be used to evaluate the quality of the tool when applied to unseen EHRs.

● 2.3 Hardware requirements for the NLP component

Although the training phase of large language models consumes lots of time and data to achieve the best performance and needs lots of computational resources such as GPUs, CPUs and RAM, the inference phase of the model (i.e., when the model is asked to answer a certain query), is also more important from the point of view of the computational resources, since the model must be deployed and run in hospital EDs, where it is likely not to have powerful computational resources.

Consequently, the vital practical question is “what are the minimum hardware requirements of a hospital server to execute the model?”

In order to answer the aforementioned question, several experiments based on a large language model, called mT5-large, are conducted. Given a specific hardware configuration, the main objective is to estimate how much time is needed to process an unstructured medical text.

To describe the experimental study, we address the following issues:

- Information processing task
- Hardware Configurations
- Dataset
- Configuration and Setting Parameters
- Evaluation Metrics
- Experimental Study

2.3.1 Information Processing Task

An abstractive medical text summarization system has been chosen to process medical documents. Text summarization is an NLP task that involves constructing a brief and well-structured summary of a lengthy text document. This process entails identifying and emphasizing the text's critical information and essential points within the text. The process is referred to as document summarization when applied to a specific document.

Document summarization approaches are of two major types [8]:

- Extractive: In an extractive summary, the output comprises the most relevant and important information from the source document.
- Abstractive: In an abstractive summary, the output is more creative and insightful. The content is not copied from the original document.

The main reason to choose this task is that text summarization is a kind of generative task mostly used for information extraction.

2.3.2 Hardware Configurations

Three different hardware configurations (see Table 2) have been assumed in this study.

Table 2. Hardware Configurations

Characteristics	Config 1	Config 2	Config 3
Device	CPU	CPU	GPU (single)
Model	Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4316 CPU @	AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2920X	A40 (46GB)
Frequency	2.30GHz	2.10GHz	2.30GHz
No. Device	2	1	1
Cores	20	12	-

2.3.3 Dataset

MeQSum[1] consists of 1,000 questions collected from the U.S. National Library of Medicine, which are annotated by summaries written by three medical experts. In addition to the text of the message, the subject is also specified for most questions.

Some statistics about the dataset are reported in Table 3. This dataset is frequently used in shared tasks in the medical domain.

Table 3. Some statistics about the datasets, including the number of samples and the minimum, maximum and average length of sources (input) and targets (output)

Dataset	# Samples	Source (Tokens)			Target (Summarised Questions) (# Tokens)		
		Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg
MeQSUM	1,000	7	417	66.40	6	43	14.37

2.3.4 Configurations and Setting Parameters

The baselines are implemented in python on the hardware configurations reported in Table 2. Table 4 reports the values of all parameters.

Table 4. Setting Parameters

Parameters	Value
Optimizer	AdamW
Learning rate	2E-5
Batch size	4
# Epoch	10
Embedding size	768
Dropout rate	0.1
Max -input -length	512
# Workers	4
Warmup	0
Precision	32 bits
Max-output-length	35
Min-output-length	5
Label smoothing	0.1
#beams	4

2.3.5 Evaluation Metrics

The effectiveness of the model in terms of quality is computed based on BERTScore, Rouge-N (Recall) and Rouge-N (F1-measure), whereas the performance of the model in terms of computation time over the given configurations (See Table 2) is computed based on TPT and TPS metrics.

- **Rouge-N** (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation): Rouge [3] is one of the most widely used evaluation metrics for text summarization tasks. Rouge-N (RECALL) divides the number of overlapping N-grams between the reference summary and the generated summary by the total number of N-grams in the reference summary. Rouge-N values lie in the range of [0..1]. Although Rouge-N ensures the model captures the reference sequence's information as much as possible, it does not consider the word order when N is small. In this

case, Rouge-L is recommended in which the longest common sequences of words (LCS), which are not necessarily consecutive, is regarded. Rouge-N (Precision) points to the proportion of words suggested by the generated summary that actually appear in the reference summary. Accordingly, Rouge-N (F1-measure) is the harmonic mean of Rouge-N (Recall) and Rouge-N (precision). In this study, all Rouge-1, Rouge-2, Rouge-3 and Rouge-L are reported.

- **BERTScore [9]:** It is an evaluation metric for text generation tasks, introduced in 2019. In contrast to Rouge metrics, which measure syntactic similarity, BERTScore focuses on computing semantic similarity between the reference sequence and the generated sequence. First, the contextualized word embedding of both sequences is obtained by passing them to a BERT-based transformer model. Second, the cosine similarity score is calculated for each token in the reference sequence with respect to every token of the generated sequence. Lastly, recall is computed by doing a greedy matching.
- **TPT (Time Per Token):** indicates the time needed to process a single token in order to produce a summary. It is notable that although a token is not a word, for simplicity, here it is assumed that a token equals a word.
- **TPP (Time Per Page):** indicates the time needed to process a single page, which contains nearly 250 words, in order to produce a summary.

2.3.6 Experimental study (Results and Conclusions)

To evaluate the model, two main evaluation scenarios have been followed. First, the model has been compared with its rival in terms of quality metrics, which are reported in Table 5. Second, to address running time, the proposed model runs over different configurations (See Table 2), whose results are reported in Table 6. In the first evaluation scenario, it is notable that all models ran on 4 GPUs.

Table 5. Comparison of Medical mT5-large with mT5-large

Model	Metric	Loss values
M: Medical mT5-large (ours)	BERTScore(f): 0.885 Rouge-1 (f): 0.383 Rouge-2 (f): 0.213 Rouge-3 (f): 0.125 Rouge-4 (f): 0.066 Rough-L (f): 0.331	Loss(train):2.75 Loss(dev): 2.58
M: mT5-large	BERTScore(f): 0.863 Rouge-1 (f): 0.314 Rouge-2 (f): 0.129 Rouge-3 (f): 0.061 Rouge-4 (f): 0.026 Rough-L (f): 0.252	Loss(train):2.80 Loss(dev): 2.55

Table 5 shows that our model is slightly better than its rival in terms of all quality metrics. It achieves 0.022, 0.069 and 0.079 points improvements in BERTScore, Rouge-1(F1), and Rouge-L(F1),

respectively. In other words, our model generates more qualified summaries than its rival in terms of semantic, lexicon and word order.

Table 6. A comparison of inference time of our model over the three hardware configurations

Characteristics	Task: Medical Summarization Phase: Inference Dataset: MeqSUM No. Sentence: 99 No. Token: 5196 No. Generated Token:975 Model: Med T5-large	Task: Medical Summarization Phase: Inference Dataset: MeqSUM No. Sentence: 99 No. Token: 5196 No. Generated Token:975 Model: Med T5-large	Task: Medical Summarization Phase: Inference Dataset: MeqSUM No. Sentence: 99 No. Token: 5196 No. Generated Token:975 Model: Med T5-large
Configuration	Machine A	Machine B	Machine C
Device	CPU	CPU	GPU (single)
Model	Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4316 CPU @ 2.30GHz	AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2920X 2.10GHz	A40 (46GB)
No. Device	2	1	1
Cores	20	12	-
Device Usage	100%	100%	100%
Mem Usage	17.5GB	17.5GB	17.1 GB
Disk Usage	9.5GB	9.5GB	9.5GB
Loading Time (Model)	16 Sec	14Sec	18 Sec
Time per Token (TPT)	54.6 mSec	135 mSec	25 mSec
Time per Page(TPP)	30.35 Sec	74.4 Sec	13.7 Sec

As Table 6 reports, although memory usage, disk usage and loading time stay nearly the same for all three hardware configurations, significant differences are observed when we consider TPT and TPP. Machine C is nearly two times and six times faster than Machine A and Machine B, respectively. In order to answer the main practical question, it is needed to know how many tokens or pages are supposed to process during a day in an emergency department of a hospital and then which of the given machines is able to process them.

Simply, it could be calculated that Machines A, B and C are able to process 2,847, 1,162 and 6,171 pages per day, respectively.

Based on Limb [2] and Ramsey et al.[5], on average, an emergency department normally has 60K–90K admissions per year (166 - 247 admissions per day). Also, if we assume that for every patient 5 pages of medical narratives are normally produced while they are staying in an emergency department of a hospital, the hospital needs to process about 1,233 pages per day in the worst case. Therefore, based on the assumptions and considering pre-processing and post-processing tasks, it could be concluded that, given the ordinary workload of an emergency department of a hospital, the configuration of Machine A is enough as minimum hardware requirement.

3. Assessment and selection of the reference resources to be used for NLP processing

In WP1, we will collect an adequate amount of EHRs and related data to be used to develop the NLP models.

The activity includes the following steps:

- collection of in-domain documents (e.g., medical scientific publications) for each language (1M+ documents for each language);
- collection of unlabelled EHR reports (20K+) for each language;
- production of annotated “gold” data (2K+ EHR) for each language; integration with already existing datasets (e.g., MIMIC, E3C, etc.); split of the data in training/dev/test;
- estimation of the gold data quality for each language, based on standard indicators (e.g., inter-annotator agreement).

As provided in the GANTT of the project, this task started during the first year of the project, but it is still ongoing. Particularly, the data collection of EHR records is not concluded and data annotation will take place after that.

● 3.1 Non-annotated resources for pre-training medical large language models

The first of the steps above (i.e., the collection of medical documents) has already been partially carried out, while the other will be carried out in task T1.2. As for the in-domain documents, we are building upon the work already performed in the ANTIDOTE EU project (CALL CHIST-ERA 2019 XAI; <https://univ-cotedazur.eu/antidote>). In ANTIDOTE, FBK created the Italian CommonCrawl Medical Corpus (ICCMC). The starting point was a subset of the Clean Italian mC4 Corpus (https://huggingface.co/datasets/gstarti/clean_mc4_it), the Italian split and cleaned version of the Multilingual Colossal CommonCrawl’s web crawl Corpus (mC4: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/mc4>). With some scripts, the documents coming from medical websites were selected (approximately 67 Million words). Then, such a corpus was extended with other documents from the medical domain: drug leaflets (30 Million words), Wikipedia medicine pages (13 M), E3C (11 M), university theses (5 M), PubMed articles (2 M), and other, smaller sources. In total, 143 million words.

Exploiting the documents mentioned above for Italian (and medical documents for English, French and Spanish), the first version of Medical mT5 was built. We are currently testing the performance of the model in different NLP tasks.

In eCREAM, the corpus has been further extended thanks to the availability of medical scientific publications (journals, books, etc.) made freely available by Italian publishers (specifically, Il Pensiero Scientifico Editore and Zadig) and of university medicine theses downloaded from other sources.

- **3.2 Annotated resources for fine-tuning a language model on eCREAM tasks**

We created a set of false EHRs, with the help of two Italian ED clinicians, in which we included information that the system should recognize and then proceeded to annotate them. This first database serves to test the language model. Concerning the fine-tuning of the language model, we are currently laying out a protocol for the collection of a sample of EHRs that will be anonymized and will serve for the training.

4. Definition of the NLP tasks

- **4.1 eCREAM's benchmark for NLP**

FBK, together with Orobix and IRFMN, noted the importance of building a benchmark to evaluate the performance of artificial intelligence models, so a new activity was proposed and approved.

The objective is the creation of a benchmark that can be used to test the abilities of a Large Language Model (LLM) to address several textual tasks (e.g., question answering, information extraction, text classification, text generation) in the medical domain, with particular emphasis on emergency medicine (EM).

The need for a shared benchmark in the medical domain arises from several facts: (i) although there are already datasets for various NLP tasks in the medical area, there is no unified benchmark that can be used as a reference for the whole domain; (ii) the recent progress and performance of pre-trained LLMs have set the bar higher than in the past, which requires more comprehensive tasks to be addressed; (iii) the large diffusion of prompting engineering to query LLMs allows the designing of tasks that do not require extensive annotation effort, opening a wide range of new benchmarking possibilities. The eCREAM benchmark aims at establishing a reference benchmark able to challenge high-performing language models, including those based on instruction-following fine-tuning (e.g., GPT-3.5, GPT-4, Alpaca, Dolly, Cerebras, LLAMA-2, etc.). The benchmark has the following innovative characteristics: (i) tasks are close to end-to-end applications in clinical practice, rather than intermediate tasks typically proposed in NLP (e.g., named entity recognition); (ii) tasks include both traditional supervised datasets, with training and test data split, and few-shot tasks, with only a few training examples. With the aim of encouraging model generalizability, we expect that eCREAM benchmark participants will use a single language model for all the tasks of the benchmark, rather than fine-tuning a model on single tasks.

The eCREAM benchmark is organized into *tasks* considered relevant in the medical domain and representative of potential applications in emergency medicine (e.g., predicting a diagnosis given a certain clinical case). A task typically consists of test data with the correct solution of the task (e.g., a thousand clinical cases with their correct diagnoses assigned by experts), and the goal of the benchmark is to test the performance of an automatic system on the tasks. In order to minimize the construction effort, several tasks of the benchmark will be collected from already existing available data.

A number of criteria can be considered for task selection in the eCREAM benchmark design:

- **General Medical Domain (GMD) vs. Emergency Medicine (EM):** although the benchmark mainly targets the EM domain, some of the tasks are general for the medical domain. In addition, it might

be easier, at least in the initial phase of the project, to collect datasets for the general medical domain.

- **Supervised vs. unsupervised (fine-tuning vs. prompting):** A task can be either supervised (i.e., the task includes both training and test data), or unsupervised (i.e., the task includes test data only). While previous benchmarks (e.g., GLUE, GLGE) are focused on supervised tasks, where training data are used to fine-tune the language model, the recent progress of LLMs technologies showed that prompt-learning approaches can be competitive with very large models. In this perspective, the eCREAM benchmark includes a large number of unsupervised tasks to be experimented through prompting.
- **Languages:** each task in the benchmark can be proposed in more than one language, e.g., by automatically translating the task from one language to another. This option is still under discussion.
- **Public vs. hidden test.** The eCREAM benchmark includes datasets that are publicly available, i.e., the test data are known. However, it might make sense to include a small proportion of tasks whose test data are unknown to the participants, to increase the fairness of the benchmark.
- **Difficulty of the task.** Tasks selected for the eCREAM benchmark should be challenging for the current state-of-the-art LLMs, in order to maintain their interest for an extended amount of time.
- **Type of NLP task.** The benchmark design is structured along a few high-level categories, corresponding to distinctions largely adopted in the NLP field:
 - **Text classification:** here the input is a medical document, and the model has to classify the document under a set of predefined categories. For instance, the classification of a radiological report according to a predefined set of diagnoses (e.g., ICD-10 codes).
 - **Information extraction:** the input is a medical document and the model has to mark portions of the document that are relevant given a set of classes. For instance, individuating all portions of a discharge letter that mention a pathology. Information extraction can be coupled with an entity linking task, where a textual mention is mapped (linked) to a corresponding concept in a medical repository (e.g., UMLS). Entity linking requires the availability of the knowledge repository.
 - **Semantic inference:** the input is two sentences in the medical domain and the model has to predict the semantic relation between them. For instance, the degree of semantic similarity of the sentences.
 - **Question answering:** the input is a question and the model has to return an answer, with supporting information. For instance, answering a multiple choice test, such as admission tests at medical faculties.
 - **Knowledge elicitation:** the input is a query addressing general or specific medical knowledge, and the answer of the model should be validated against knowledge in a medical repository (e.g., UMLS). For instance, solve an acronym in the medical domain, or list subclasses of a certain class.
 - **Text generation:** here the goal is to generate a new text given an input request. Examples include generating a summary of a longer document, or an explanation for a certain medical fact (e.g., a diagnosis).

The following table summarizes the list of eight tasks which are currently under consideration to be included in the benchmark.

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
1	During triage, the nurse should select the main symptom for the patient's access to the PS. In some cases instead of selecting a specific symptom, the nurse chooses an undefined "other." The purpose of the task is to identify the main symptom (on average the most dangerous one) from the nurse's free text, substituting "other," to speed up the clinician's activities at the time of admission	A text written by a nurse in triage: "Accesses ED with ambulance. Found on the ground by her children. Presents with significant fronto-parietal hematoma"	Neurological disorder	Classification among predefined categories (about 20 categories of symptoms)
2	Assignment of triage code, given vital parameters (saturation, blood pressure, body temperature, etc.), anamnesis and objective examination at access to the ED.	Objective examination: "Pt responsive only to painful stimulus, tachypnea Parameters: SpO2 85%. BP 80/40. T° 35,6 Age: 89 Pain scale: 0	A triage code, for example "Rosso", according to the Italian coding system	Classification among five predefined categories (the Italian triage codes)
3	Predict whether the patient will undergo diagnostic imaging examinations in the ED and, if so, which examinations, considering as input the info collected during the triage, the anamnesis, the objective examination upon access to ED, and the results of the laboratory tests he was subjected to.	Objective examination: "Pt responsive only to painful stimulus, tachypnea Parameters: SpO2 92%. BP: 80/40. T° 39° Age: 56 Pain scale: 2 Albumin: 4 Creatinine: 3	A list that includes possible diagnostic imaging examinations to which the patient should be subjected, for example: [abdominal CT scan]	Text generation (the model should suggest what imaging examinations the patient will have to undergo by also indicating the body district to be examined)

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
4	Predict whether the patient will undergo laboratory tests after accessing the ED and, if so, which examinations, considering the info collected during the triage, the anamnesis and the objective examination upon access to the ED.	Objective examination: "Pt responsive only to painful stimulus, tachypnea Parameters: SpO2 92%. BP: 80/40. T° 39° Age: 56 Pain scale: 5	A list that includes possible laboratory exams to which the patient should be subjected, for example: [albumin level, creatinine level]	Text generation (the model should suggest what laboratory tests the patient will have to undergo)
5	Selection of the diagnosis at the time of discharge from the ED from a pre-selected number (around 1000) of possible options, analyzing all the information collected in ED, i.e., the entire clinical case.	Accessed for an episode of TLOC preceded by dizziness and blurred vision on her way to the bathroom; not trauma because she was supported by her husband. - lives at home with husband (caregiver), dependent on husband for ADLs, does not walk, sits in wheelchair at home, postural transitions helped by her husband. - hypertension - COPD - diabetes mellitus - diverticulosis - Alzheimer's dementia Therapy at home: donezepil, zopranol, isoptin, esomeprazole, linagliptin, fast-acting insulin, atorvastatin - Denies drug allergies - vaccinated 5 doses for sars cov2	Syncope/pre-syncope	Classification

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
		<p>Patient alert, discreetly oriented about the situation; amnesic about the event</p> <p>BP 110/60 mmHg; Tilt test in normal range HR 80 bpm Euthermic SpO2 96% in room air Heart Auscultation: valid, rhythmic tones Thoracic Auscultation: diffuse Normal Breath Sounds Dry mucous membranes</p> <p>At ultrasounds: no pericardial effusion, left ventricular kinesis in the normal range, no alterations in right ventricular kinesis, small and collapsing vena cava</p> <p>ECG: Normal Sinus Rhythm, HR 81 bpm, intermediate QRS, no ST changes Venous blood gas analysis: pH 7.42, Hb 9.7, Na 140, K 4.08, Gly 250, Lac 1.7</p>		
6	Distinction between an acute or chronic clinical problem, such as a clearly pathologically altered hemoglobin or saturation or creatinine value, considering as input outcomes of laboratory tests and vital parameters,	Male, 76 years old. Admitted to the ED for fever for about 3 days (T°C max 38) associated with cough with sputum, dyspnea on minimal exertion, accessory muscle use. Has already taken antibiotic therapy at	The reduction in SpO2 is of acute origin. Explanation: the patient does not have chronic pulmonary disease and has acute pneumonia	Classification (to distinguish between acute and chronic disease) and text generation (to explain the rationale followed to select the acute or chronic class).

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
	<p>as well as recent and remote history, possibly pharmacological. The model should also explain the rationale followed to distinguish between acute and chronic disease.</p>	<p>home with little benefit.</p> <p>-Ex-smoker (until 30y ago).</p> <p>-Myelodysplastic syndrome with thrombocytopenia and splenomegaly</p> <p>-Previous pneumonias</p> <p>Denies allergies</p> <p>BP 130/75</p> <p>SpO2 89% in room air</p> <p>RR 24</p> <p>T°C 36</p> <p>Vigilant, oriented, cooperative</p> <p>Cardiac auscultation: valid, rhythmic tones</p> <p>Thoracic auscultation: reduced Breath</p> <p>Sounds at right base, scattered hissing and buzzing at anterior fields</p> <p>No edema or signs of DVT</p> <p>Venous Blood analysis: WBC 5410, Hb 10.5, PLTS 56000, Na 133, creatinine 1.79</p> <p>Chest x-ray --> right basal pneumonia</p> <p>Is the reduction in SpO2 of acute or chronic origin?</p>		
7.1	<p>Extraction of all the clinical entities mentioned in the clinical note (regardless of denials, lack of impact on the patient as in the case of familiarity, etc.): symptoms, diseases,</p>	<p>“A 3 year old girl born from non-consanguineous parents, without any neonatal suffering; with good psychomotor development, from a</p>	<p>A list of all the clinical entities reported in the clinical note, for example:</p> <p>['exophthalmia', 'unilateral</p>	<p>Information extraction</p>

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
	problems, therapies, examinations should be considered as categories to be annotated.	popular district in one of our cities, without any obvious contact with dogs; presented with exophthalmia associated with unilateral blindness evolving rapidly within 3 months. Clinical examination showed a non-pulsatile, painless, axial, irreducible exophthalmia with no sign of conjunctivitis or keratitis, and right monocular 5 blindness, right ptosis; and fundal examination had objectified right papillary oedema.”	blindness', 'exophthalmia', 'conjunctivitis', 'keratitis', 'monocular blindness', 'right ptosis', 'right papillary oedema']	
7.2	Identification of tests (laboratory tests, but also others) and their results in a clinical case and linkage of the test to the respective result.	“Pertinent laboratory studies included a hemoglobin level of 10 g/dL, platelet count was normal, blood urea of 1,2 g/l (0,18-0,45 g/L), and a creatinine level of 68 mg/L (7-13 mg/L).”	A list of all the tests reported in the clinical note with their results, for example: [hemoglobin 10 g/dL platelet count normal blood urea 1,2 g/l creatinine 68 mg/L]	Information extraction
7.3	Identification of problems, treatments, and tests in clinical cases and extraction of the relationship between them, such as “the treatment improves the problem”, “the test reveals a problem”, etc. The possible relationships	“A follow-up CT scan was done which did not show any evidence for splenomegaly or hepatomegaly”	A tuple with 2 problems/treatments/tests and their relation, such as: [“follow-up CT scan”, “TeEP”, “splenomegaly”][“follow-up CT scan”, “TeEP”, “hepatomegaly”]	Information extraction and text classification

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
	<p>to be identified are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TrIP: a treatment has improved or cured a problem ● TrWP: a medical problem has worsened because of, or in spite of, a treatment ● TrCP: a treatment caused a problem ● TrAP: a treatment administered for a problem. ● TrNAP: a treatment was avoided because of a problem. ● TeRP: a test has revealed a problem. ● TeCP: a test was performed to investigate a problem. ● PIP: two problems are related to each other. ● TeEP: a test excluded a problem 			
7.4	<p>Identification of mentioned diseases/symptoms and their classification into:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● known: ongoing problem, already known in the anamnesis ● acute: ongoing acute problem, for 	<p>“Reflex testing of at-risk relatives confirmed that both of his parents were heterozygous carriers of the same mutation. “Given his asymptomatic clinical course, he remains under close follow-up without requiring any</p>	<p>A list of all the diseases/symptoms reported in the clinical note with their classification in known, acute, discovered, resolved, or familiarity, for example:</p>	<p>Information extraction and text classification</p>

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
	<p>example the reason for admission to the ED</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> discovered: problem that emerged from investigations performed during or following the ER stay resolved: problem present in the past, but from which the patient has recovered familiarity: the patient does not have it, but some family members do 	<p>specific treatment for pancreatic insufficiency.”</p>	<p>[' both of his parents were heterozygous carriers of the same mutation', 'familiarity'], ['pancreatic insufficiency', 'known']</p>	
7.5	<p>Partition of examinations performed at different moments</p>	<p>“This is a case report of a 59-year old woman with a 5-year clinical history of perimenopausal uterine bleeding and three explorative curettages. Gynecological and ultrasound examinations revealed ovarian enlargement with a diameter of 50 mm with hypoechoic zones suspected of benign teratoma.”</p>	<p>A list of all the examinations reported in the clinical note and the execution period, for example:</p> <p>[['Gynecological and ultrasound examination', 'exam0'], ['diagnostic test such as Ca-125, AFP, free-T4 and TSH', 'exam0'], ['biopsy', 'exam0'], ['histopathology', 'exam1']]</p>	<p>Information extraction</p>
7.6	<p>Distinction between denials/assertions in the text</p>	<p>"A follow-up CT scan was done which did not show any evidence for</p>	<p>A list of the diseases/symptoms reported in the clinical note with</p>	<p>Information extraction and text classification</p>

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
		splenomegaly or hepatomegaly. She went for a debridement of her left calf lesion on 10/2/93 and was started empirically on IV ceftriaxone which was changed to doxycycline on the day of discharge.”	their classification in present or absent, such as: ['hepatomegaly', 'absent'], ['splenomegaly', 'absent'], ['her left calf lesion', 'present']]	
7.7	Identification of the drugs mentioned in the clinical note with their dosing at different moments	“In May 2014 a 49 year-old gentleman was admitted for widespread mucocutaneous blistering diagnosed as PV by histology and immunofluorescence. After 6 weeks of treatment with systemic steroids and azathioprine the patient developed pulmonary emboli and started oral anticoagulation with warfarin. In late September, the patient re-presented with a severe flare of PV and a recurrent deep vein thrombosis despite oral anticoagulation within therapeutic range. Warfarin was changed to subcutaneous low molecular heparin in therapeutic dose while treatment for pemphigus was escalated: first azathioprine was switched to mycophenolate	A list of the therapies reported in the clinical note and the time of their delivery, such as: [["systemic steroids", "dosing non specified", "therapy0"], ["azathioprine", "dosing non specified", "therapy0"], ["warfarin", "within therapeutic range", "therapy1"]]	Information extraction

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
		mofetil and the steroids dose increased.”		
8	Resolution of multiple-choice admission test for medical school in Italy, in particular for the emergency medicine.	<p>Questions from Italian medical school admission tests, such as:</p> <p>Which of the following Scores is used to assess the severity of a patient with cirrhosis of the liver?’</p> <p>A: GCS B: Chads-VASC C: ABCD D: Child-Pugh E: Curb-65</p>	<p>Answer to the multiple choice questions, such as:</p> <p>[D: Child-Pugh]</p>	Multiple choice question answering
9	Translation of unstructured clinical ED notes into structured medical records: information on specific variables that, according to a team of physicians involved in the project, are of interest in the recognition and treatment of TLOC and Dyspnea must be extracted.	<p>Accessed for aggravating dyspnea for one month, weight loss of about 10 kg, hyporexia and edema in feet, frequent belching.</p> <p>Poorly rested nights for the past month.</p> <p>Recent bereavement.</p> <p>- Emphysematous asthmatic COPD.</p> <p>- suspected k lung found in Left Upper Lobe in July 2021, placed on follow up due to exiguity of non-biopsiable lesion. At last staging available from documentation (01/2022): appearance of other parenchymal</p>	<p>A structured medical record, such as:</p> <p>[Temperature: 36.7, Allergy: False Vascular disease: True, Neoplasia: True, etc.]</p>	<p>Information extraction/classification.</p> <p>The variables to be considered are of 3 types:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous with numerical values (for example the body temperature) • Categorical dichotomous (for example allergy presence) • Categorical with more than 2 levels (such as the level of consciousness AVPU)

#	Emergency department activity	Example input	Example output	NLP task
		<p>nodulations in Left Upper Lobe, Right Upper Lobe appearance of nodulations with spiculated margins.</p> <p>- indication for evaluation Interdisciplinary Care Groups.</p> <p>Therapy at home: Ventolin, Trimbrow 2 puff x 2.</p> <p>No known drug allergies</p> <p>Fair general condition. GCS 15, oriented in space-time and cooperative. Cachectic</p> <p>BP: 127/68, HR: 98, SpO2: 94%, RR: 18, T°: 36.7, GCS: 15, Pain: 0.</p> <p>Valid and rhythmic heart tones.</p> <p>Normal Breath Sounds diffusely reduced, bibasal velcro noises.</p> <p>Abdomen flat, tractable, not achy or painful,</p> <p>peristalsis +. Blumberg and Murphy negative. Skin well perfused, edema on dorsum of feet bilaterally</p>		

Following the experience of both GLUE and GLGE, the evaluation of the eCREAM benchmark is based on the evaluation of each task independently. An overall score is provided as the unweighted average of the tasks. In case more than one metric (e.g., Rouge-1 and Rouge-2 for text generation tasks, or accuracy and F1 for information extraction) is required for a task, the result of the task is the unweighted average of the metrics.

Most of the metrics used in NLP (e.g., accuracy, F1, MRR, Rouge, Bleu) are scaled with values between 0 and 1, which makes them comparable. However, in case of tasks with metrics with very low values (e.g., 0,01), it might be reasonable to rescale the values in order to make them comparable to the other tasks.

The website of the eCREAM benchmark will allow users to download the dataset and provide a submission page for automatic evaluation. Results are uploaded through files, one for each task in the benchmark, reporting the identifier of the corresponding case in the test-set and the result (label, number, sentence) obtained by the model.

Results are then displayed (if agreed in the submission form) on a leaderboard page (see the GLUE webpage).

- [4.2 T5-large medical model](#)

Large language models are a type of artificial intelligence (AI) model designed to understand and generate human-like text based on the input they receive. These models are built using deep learning techniques, particularly using architectures like transformers, which have proven highly effective in natural language processing tasks.

The term "large" in large language models refers to the vast number of parameters or weights that these models have. These parameters are learned from massive amounts of text data during a training process. The more parameters a model has, the more complex and nuanced patterns it can capture from the data, resulting in improved performance on various language-related tasks.

Notable examples of large language models are T5, BART, ChatGPT and so on. These models are trained on diverse and extensive text corpora to develop a broad understanding of human language, enabling them to perform tasks such as language translation, text generation, question answering, summarization, sentiment analysis, and more.

Large language models have gained significant attention for their potential to revolutionize various industries, including customer service, content generation, language translation, and even creative writing. They have shown the ability to produce coherent and contextually relevant text, making them valuable tools for both practical applications and research in the field of AI and natural language processing.

T5, which stands for "Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer" [7], is a language model architecture developed by Google's AI research team. It is based on the transformer architecture, which has proven highly effective for various natural language processing tasks. T5, however, introduces a

unified framework where all tasks are reformulated as text-to-text tasks, meaning both the input and output are treated as text strings.

In the traditional transformer architecture, tasks like machine translation, text classification, and text generation are treated differently, each requiring a specific design and fine-tuning process. T5 simplifies this by framing all tasks as a text-generation task. This means that any NLP task, whether it is translation, summarization, question answering, or others, can be cast as converting an input text into an output text.

T5's architecture allows it to be pre-trained on a large corpus of text data, learning the nuances of language and various linguistic patterns. After pre-training, the model can be fine-tuned on specific tasks by providing task-specific data and adjusting the model's parameters accordingly.

mT5, short for "Multilingual Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer," is an extension of the T5 architecture specifically designed for multilingual natural language processing tasks. It was developed by Google's AI research team as an evolution of the original T5 model to handle multiple languages in a single model.

Although T5 treats various NLP tasks as text-to-text tasks, mT5 extends this concept to handle multiple languages. It can perform a wide range of tasks across different languages using the same unified architecture. This is particularly useful in scenarios involving data in which multiple languages are involved, as it allows for efficient cross-lingual transfer of knowledge.

The architecture of mT5 is similar to that of T5, but with enhancements to handle multilingual data. It is pre-trained on a diverse, multilingual corpus, allowing it to learn patterns and representations across languages. After pre-training, mT5 can be fine-tuned for specific multilingual tasks, such as translation, language modeling, text classification, and more.

mT5 has demonstrated impressive capabilities in multilingual settings and has achieved state-of-the-art performance on various cross-lingual tasks. It simplifies the process of building models that can work across multiple languages without needing separate models for each language or task, making it a valuable tool for multilingual natural language processing applications.

mT5 [7] is pre-trained on a new Common Crawl-based dataset covering 101 languages, including French, German, Italian, and Spanish. Regarding size, mT5 has been available in five different sizes, as follows.

Table1. mT5 variants released by Google

Models	# parameters
small	60M
Base	220M

Large	770M
3B	3B
11B	11B

In order to develop a new AI-based solution to extract high-quality and highly structured clinical knowledge from unstructured medical resources including Electronic Health Records (EHRs), discharges and so on, it is necessary to develop and deploy a machine learning model based on large language models getting through training, evaluation and inference phases by taking task-specific data. In the training and evaluation phases, the learnable parameters of the model must first be trained by labeled and unlabeled medical data in supervised and unsupervised manners, and then plenty of experimental studies must be carried out to assess the quality of generated outputs in the evaluation phase. Note that these phases need tremendous memory capacity and computational resources. Moreover, the inference phase starts the process of running live data points in a model to calculate an output. In other words, this phase puts the model into production to extract accurate structured medical information. Logically, the model must be deployed in hospitals to have access to live data.

mT5-large has been chosen for the current study and pre-trained in medical documents in an unsupervised manner and then fine-tuned by medical questions over the MeQSUM dataset in a supervised manner. The best performance of mT5-large, reported so far, is the essential reason for this selection.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable reports on Task 1.1, “Context analysis and task definition”, aiming to perform an analysis of the requirements for applying NLP techniques to the unstructured portion of EHRs in EDs and to define the NLP tasks useful for emergency physicians and nurses. The task, according to the project plan, includes the following activities:

- *Analysis of the context and the requirements for each emergency department of the project* (Section 2); There are three main aspects we have been working on: an initial workflow involving the NLP component (in collaboration with Astir); an anonymization component ensuring that the NLP component manages data without sensible information during the training of the model (Section 2.2); and an initial study of the hardware requirements of the NLP component at inference time, in order to test the compatibility with current hardware available in EDs (Section 2.3).
- *Assessment and selection of the reference resources to be used for NLP processing* (Section 3). We are considering two kinds of resources: non-annotated resources, necessary for pre-training large language models in the medical domain (Section 3.1) and annotated resources, necessary to train a language model on the specific tasks of eCREAM (Section 3.2).

- *Definition of the NLP tasks, in terms of the clinical entities to be automatically extracted (Section 4).* In the first year of the project we worked on the following aspects: an initial definition of the eCREAM tasks related to NLP, presented as the eCREAM benchmark (Section 4.1); an assessment of the available language models in the medical domain, including initial work on a T5-large medical model (Section 4.2).

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